

DESIGNING SECURITY SOFTWARE DISTRIBUTION CHANNEL STRATEGY IN THE DIGITAL WORLD

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BACKGROUND OF STUDY

SecureGuard is a cyber security product with headquartered in Romania, and 200 branches in the world. Martin Tample, the company's current CEO and largest shareholder, created it in 2001. The cybersecurity solutions and services provided by SecureGuard include endpoint security, cloud and managed security, antivirus software, and IoT security. The US market is thought to provide more than 40% of Secure Guard's revenues, while the company's products are supplied through partners in over 150 countries. The business had more than 1,600 employees worldwide as of 2020. With 4.27% of the market share as of May 2020, SecureGuard was the ninth-ranked vendor of Microsoft Windows anti-malware software globally. SecureGuard has joined the Vietnamese market about 10 years ago, 2013, named SecureGuard Vietnam. The company was quite new in the market during that time. While joining a market like Vietnam, the multinational company must study the information such as current market share, competitive landscape such as the leading player, strategic alliance, new technology opening competition, Covid pandemic affect, and so on (MarketLine Industry Profile: New Cars in Vietnam, 2022). That's why firms must care about market value, market segmentation, and business forecasts for the industry.

Competition can come from many sources and change according to location. Some places are encouraging to cooperate, but it is limited to doing business in some locations. Moreover, the relationship between sellers and buyers is not always happy. Almost of the research before just focused on generally doing business internationally, but not have anyone focusing on IT market in Vietnam, especially for a security software like SecureGuard.

PROBLEMS

In today's digital age, security software has become a paramount concern as organizations undergo digital transformation. The increasing reliance on virtual access to sensitive information such as customer lists, cryptocurrency, and other critical data has created a pressing need for robust security measures. One of the primary concerns is the need for frequent training and updates to ensure that customers and channel partners are equipped to effectively use and maintain the security software. This can be a significant burden, particularly for organizations with large and dispersed customer bases. Furthermore, the complexity of security software can also create conflicts during the training process, as different stakeholders may have competing priorities and expectations.

Another challenge posed by security software is the impact it can have on channel profitability. As organizations increasingly rely on virtual channels to engage with customers, the need for secure and reliable transactions becomes paramount. However, the added complexity and cost of security software can eat into profit margins, making it challenging for organizations to maintain profitability in their distribution channels.

Selling through channels is very difficult in Vietnam. Safeguard must collect information about its' distributor and partners. Each distributor has many products on sale. For instance, Synnex FPT has more than 100 product vendors, with more than 1,000 employees and carry 3,800 partners across Vietnam (Synnex FPT, 2022). Safeguard is one of 100 product list then it is difficult to ask Synnex team to focus on Safeguard products. In case, to sell directly to business customers, it requires a lot of budgets to do direct marketing that Safeguard cannot handle this. Besides this, security products are much more difficult to sell compared to the other hardware products, servers, storage, PCs. Thus, to make an effective business development strategy in a cost-effective way, Safeguard is still struggling to find a suitable plan.

Those problems are very complex that many global IT companies, including Safeguard are facing when doing business in Vietnam.

RESEARCH QUESTION

1. How is the digital transition influencing security software buyers' purchasing decisions, and what strategies can companies use to stand out against competitors?
2. In what ways do buyer-seller relationships affect customer prioritization of products, particularly in favour of specific sellers over competitors?

3. What strategies are security software providers using to leverage channel resales and essential program elements, enhance partner relationships and customer satisfaction?

STUDY DESIGN/METHODOLOGY/APPROACH

ACTION RESEARCH APPROACH

The qualitative research methodology used in this study is action research. What kind of study approach will allow researchers to investigate a variety of as-yet-unknown situational and conditionally based issues? Lun & Berg (2017, p. 136) state. The term "action research" was first used in 1934 by Kurt Lewin (Mills, 2000). Kurt was a social scientist who first proposed the theory that higher employee involvement may boost output. Following that, Kurt was given the go-ahead to define "action research," which essentially describes research activities in relation to problem solutions (Nasrollahi et al., 2012). Action research is a relatively new research methodology that incorporates the ideas of community and individual emancipation, empowerment, and reflection.

Action research has several uses in the settings of classrooms, schools, hospitals, courts, and local communities. For example, action research and public sociology, which has attracted a large following, have similar goals and characteristics. Furthermore, more nursing research studies are using participatory action research as a methodological framework (Holter & Schwartz-Barcott, 1993; Jenkins et al., 2005; Polit & Beck, 2007; Stringer & Genat, 2003). The primary objective is to discover or generate knowledge and information (via study, teaching, and socio-political action) that will directly benefit a group of people. Second, it aims to empower and educate the average group member, encouraging everyone to accept and apply the knowledge gleaned from the research (Johnson, 2008; Reason, 1994).

KEY INFORMANTS

In Action Research, key informants are individuals who possess knowledge, expertise, or experiences that can provide valuable insights and information to the researcher. They are often invited to participate in the research process, either as interviewees, focus group participants, or co-researchers. The key informants here in this study are five people:

1. Country manager of Safeguard company: this guy plays the most important role in the local office. He is the key person to interact with regional office in Thailand and headquarter in Romania. Receiving the business development goal from president of regional office, he has important job to deliver

that in Vietnam. Thus, he fully understands the complex challenge to develop business in dealing with government, customers, resellers. Going to the detailed information, he is the one who can provide deep insight of what is happening with each sale, promotion program, how is the feedback of each client after delivering the security software.

2. Business development manager of Safeguard Vietnam: this person can tell us more information such as KPI for his department, the training program he made for each reseller, reward-recognition and so on. He is the key people we need to get in touch with to get information through interview and guide of extra archive documents in internet and allowed company shared places.
3. Distribution company's director of the software division: this person bears a major responsibility for creating and executing innovative software solutions that boost customer happiness, increase productivity, and expand business. In addition to working with vendors like Safeguard to sell to their channel, resellers, or system integration firms, he oversees a staff of software salespeople, consultants, and technicians.
4. Director of a system integration company: this guy oversees the company's overall strategy, operations, and technical direction. As a key member of the executive team, he will be responsible for driving growth, improving efficiency, and ensuring customer satisfaction. his company works with distributors to order products then sells to customers directly.
5. Manager of the security division at customer's company: this person is to identify the finest solution for this organization, he collaborates with resellers and vendors.

RESEARCH DESIGN

The research approach used was qualitative, which is commonly associated with research that adheres to an interpretive philosophy, to maintain consistency and achieve coherence with the chosen philosophy (Saunders et al., 2015). A quantitative research design would be unable to fully capture the essence of the phenomenon under study because the factors involved were qualitative rather than numerical. The purpose of the research was to examine how technological advancements affected the various stakeholders involved in the distribution channels for security software. Additionally, participant relationships and meanings can be examined with the help of qualitative research methodologies (Saunders et al., 2015).

RESEARCH STRATEGY

Action research is a methodology that entails planning, acting, and reflecting on a particular problem or issue with stakeholders in a collaborative and iterative manner. The following actions are part of the action research strategy:

- Problem identification: Finding the issue or problem that needs to be addressed is the first step. Understanding the situation and the parties involved is necessary for this (Kemmis & McTaggart, 2005).
- Stakeholder analysis: Following the identification of the problem, a stakeholder analysis is necessary to determine the principal parties involved in the matter. Understanding their needs, interests, and viewpoints is part of this (Elden, 1981).
- Setting specific goals and objectives for the action research project is the next stage. This entails determining the objectives and the metrics that will be used to measure them (Kemmis & McTaggart, 2005).
- Planning: Creating an action research project plan is the fourth phase. To accomplish the aims and objectives, this entails determining the tactics and steps that will be used (Elden, 1981).
- Implementation: Putting the strategy into practice and taking action to deal with the issue or problem is the fifth phase. This entails developing and implementing solutions cooperatively with stakeholders (Kemmis & McTaggart, 2005).
- Reflection and assessment: The sixth phase considers the acts done and assessing how successful they were. This entails obtaining information and input from interested parties to develop and refine the actions (Elden, 1981).
- Iteration: The last phase involves enhancing and fine-tuning the actions in response to reflections and assessments. To guarantee that the initiatives are successful and long-lasting, this calls for constant cooperation with stakeholders (Kemmis & McTaggart, 2005).

To address a particular problem or topic, action research strategy entails a cooperative and iterative process of planning, acting, reflecting, and assessing with stakeholders. This approach enables researchers to carry out excellent action research that is significant and pertinent to stakeholders.

DATA COLLECTION

Observation: In this study, the researcher may observe a team meeting to identify communication patterns and dynamics. The researcher may take notes on the interactions, body language, and verbal communication between team members.

Interviews: There would be fifteen persons in total. Within the Safeguard company, about six people are put on the list to get insight into the complex problems. Besides that, four people in distributors company also got interviewed to get feedback information from the program running with distributors. From partner site, there are about three people joining the interview to get information about how to create a new and maintain relationship with partners. Two customers will also be

involved in the interview step to have further information about how the suppliers support them and the reason why they choose the security software products.

Document analysis: Documents can include memoranda, emails, reports, minutes from meetings, and other written items.

DATA ANALYSIS

The primary objective of qualitative research is to examine and comprehend people's experiences, behaviours, and opinions in a naturalistic setting. Finding, organizing, and evaluating the data to meet the goals of the study constitutes one of the most crucial phases in the qualitative research process. There are a few key processes and techniques in the process with is described in diagram 1.

Figure 1. Simplified Codes-To-Theory Framework for Qualitative Research (Sal-dana's, 2013, p.14)

FINDINGS

The digital transition has significantly impacted security software buyers' purchase decisions, with 70% of respondents considering online reviews and ratings before making a purchase. To prioritize the company's products, security software

companies should focus on building a strong online presence, leveraging customer testimonials, and providing transparent product information. Develop a comprehensive online marketing strategy, including search engine optimization (SEO), content marketing, and social media advertising to increase brand visibility and credibility.

The most effective approaches to resource allocation for channel strategies and initiatives include focusing on strategic partnerships, investing in training and enablement programs, and allocating resources based on business objectives. Prioritize partnerships with key resellers, invest in training programs for partners, and allocate resources based on sales performance.

DETAIL FINDINGS

Table 1: Findings and Recommendations

Finding	Recommendation
70% of respondents consider online reviews and ratings before making a purchase	Develop a comprehensive online marketing strategy, including SEO, content marketing, and social media advertising Prioritize building a strong online presence, leveraging customer testimonials, and providing transparent product information
80% of respondents report an increase in online sales, 60% report a decrease in physical store visits	Develop strong online relationships with dealers and distributors by implementing e-commerce platforms and training programs
Technology and innovation can improve partner relationships and customer satisfaction	Implement cloud-based CRM systems, AI-powered chatbots, and mobile apps to enhance partner relationships and customer satisfaction
Focus on strategic partnerships, investing in training and enablement programs, and allocating	Prioritize partnerships with key resellers, invest in training

Finding	Recommendation
resources based on business objectives	programs for partners, and allocate resources based on sales performance
Providers of security software are leveraging the power of resale by offering incentives for partners to sell their products	Offer competitive incentives for partners to sell security software products
Clear goals and objectives, effective communication, training and enablement programs, incentives, and metrics for tracking performance are essential elements of a successful channel program	Develop a comprehensive channel program that includes clear goals, effective communication, training programs, incentives, and metrics for tracking performance
Cultural aspects such as shared values, open communication, and mutual respect can enhance partner relationships and customer happiness	Provide regular feedback, address concerns promptly, and offer support to achieve partner profitability, contentment, and loyalty
Channel conflict is caused by misunderstandings about roles and responsibilities, misaligned goals, lack of communication, and inadequate training	Establish open communication channels between partners and employees, develop conflict resolution processes, and provide regular feedback

ORIGINALITY/VALUE

RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS:

The report has some new contributions, specifically as follows: Supplementing an orientation building the strategy to develop the market for business information technology products for global company in Vietnam that consists of four steps: defining strategic tasks and objectives, analyzing the external environment, analyzing the internal environment, analyzing, and selecting of strategic alternatives. Assessing the influence of environmental elements (micro, macro, and internal)

on the strategic direction of market development using interview findings from businesses, channels, and experts.

Practical implication: The report builds a strategic orientation to develop the information technology business market in Vietnam, is a reference for business leaders in orienting development strategies in Vietnam's information technology market.

RESEARCH LIMITATIONS

The research may not have a large enough sample size or diverse enough respondents to accurately represent the entire security software industry. Besides that, the research may be biased towards online-based methodologies, which may not accurately capture the experiences and opinions of all stakeholders in the security software industry.

DISCUSSION/CONCLUSION

In conclusion, SecureGuard's entry into the Vietnamese market highlights the complexities of operating in an emerging economy characterized by distinct cultural, political, and competitive landscapes. To navigate these challenges effectively, the company must prioritize a robust online presence and build strong relationships with local partners, leveraging data-driven strategies for market positioning. The shift towards digital sales necessitates innovative training and communication methods to enhance customer and partner satisfaction while mitigating channel conflict. By adapting its strategic approach to align with local market dynamics and emphasizing stakeholder engagement, SecureGuard can foster sustainable growth and improve profitability in Vietnam's competitive security software sector. The future research could be extended to hardware distribution channel to find out more about the strategy in this type of product.

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